

1 **The Forms and Structures of Chimpanzee Algae Fishing**

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21 Running title: An Action Grammar of Chimpanzee Algae Fishing

22 **Abstract**

23 Variation in the expression of behavior is a critical measure for understanding how
24 socio-ecological factors shape cognitive and behavioral evolution and adaptability.
25 Detailed descriptions of behavioral repertoires and how they are combined and
26 structured into programs of actions is an essential foundation for this work. However,
27 comparisons within and across species are made challenging where there is
28 substantial variation in the level of detail at which behaviors are described. Here, we
29 use a systematic, multi-level framework to describe a recently reported chimpanzee
30 tool use behavior—algae fishing—at three levels of granularity: Functional
31 Behavioral Categories, Behaviors, and Behavioral Elements. We then describe how
32 these units are combined into structured programs of action. Despite variation in the
33 detail at which tool use behaviors are described in the literature, we suggest that
34 chimpanzees' algae fishing repertoire is relatively large, as compared to other forms
35 of chimpanzee tool using, and flexibly deployed at each level of description. The
36 varied use of techniques by adults suggests that there is no single optimal solution
37 for algae fishing, and that chimpanzees benefit from maintaining multiple strategies
38 for this dynamic foraging challenge. We provide an example of a structured
39 framework that can be applied to describe different levels of detail and used to show
40 within- and between-task variation. Systematic frameworks that can be consistently
41 applied across species and contexts are critical for providing the like-with-like
42 comparisons necessary for robust investigations of species-level cognition and
43 behavior.

44

45 **Keywords** Action grammar, sequences, repertoire, tool use, chimpanzee, *Pan*
46 *trogodytes verus*

47

48 **1. INTRODUCTION**

49 Behavioral flexibility enables individuals to adapt to the demands of both their
50 physical and social worlds, allowing them to survive (and sometimes thrive) in
51 dynamic and diverse environments. However, not all behaviors are variably
52 expressed. Just as selection can act on the evolution of highly complex structures
53 (such as the eye; Darwin, 1859), it can lead to the production of highly complex, but
54 fixed, patterns of behavior—for example, intricately executed mating performances
55 (Tinbergen, 1951; Griffith & Ejima, 2009; Fusani *et al.*, 2014; Scholes *et al.*, 2017;
56 Wessling *et al.*, 2025b). Variation in behavior can be shaped directly by features of
57 the local environment—for example, material availability (van Berkel *et al.*, 2024;
58 O'Malley *et al.*, 2025). But, in some cases, behavioral variation reflects decisions
59 made by an individual that integrate information across multiple features of a
60 problem. These can include tailoring tools to problems (e.g., retrieving one tool to
61 obtain another that accesses a reward; Wimpenny *et al.*, 2009), adjusting tool length
62 to reward depth (Hunt *et al.*, 2006), matching tool characteristics (e.g., brush tips) to
63 the insect species targeted (Sanz *et al.*, 2014), expressing individual kinematic
64 preferences or abilities (Estienne *et al.*, 2017; Poncet *et al.*, 2022), selecting
65 materials based on their structural flexibility (Bailey *et al.*, 2014), or adjusting
66 construction materials and methods according to nest type (Permana *et al.*, 2024).
67 The ability to integrate information and choose flexibly from among multiple viable
68 solutions to a problem (variants, cf., Wessling *et al.*, 2025b) is associated with
69 heightened cognitive demands; for example, increasing load on working memory and
70 the recruitment of executive functions, such as mental set-shifting and inhibition
71 (Uddin, 2021; Haidle, 2010; Cantwell *et al.*, 2022).

72 The granularity (level of detail) with which we describe behavior influences our
73 ability to detect (or overlook) potential variation in the expression and use of
74 behaviors and our understanding of the ways in which behaviors are combined and
75 ordered (Byrne & Byrne, 1993; Mielke *et al.*, 2024). Variation in the degree of detail
76 at which a behavior is described may result in substantial differences in the variation
77 recorded by the observer both within and between individuals—so much so that
78 studies of the same task, coded to different degrees of detail have been used to
79 argue both for (Byrne & Russon, 1998; Byrne *et al.*, 2011) and against (Tennie *et al.*,
80 2008) capacities such as social imitation in non-human species. At the same time,
81 not all forms of potentially perceptible variation are relevant to every research
82 question (e.g., gripping a tool between the second and third, or second and fourth
83 digits might be functionally equivalent, despite differing in form), and very detailed
84 cataloguing of all forms of every detectable variation of a behavior represents a
85 substantial time-burden (Grund *et al.*, 2024). Nevertheless, there is likely some level
86 of detail and systematic structure that warrants consistent application across studies,
87 particularly when a behavior is relatively new, and our understanding of which
88 features are relevant remains limited. Systematic frameworks of behavioral
89 description allow more robust understanding of relative repertoire sizes, repertoire
90 overlap (both within and across species), and cognitive abilities, which in turn enable
91 systematic, widespread comparison of behavioral units both across and within tasks
92 and species (Wessling *et al.*, 2025b).

93 Tool use is a taxonomically widespread example of a behavior that often
94 (though not always) requires behavioral flexibility for successful execution.
95 Individuals can express behavioral flexibility by varying their use of elements from
96 within a set (or ‘repertoire’) of options—the larger the set, the greater the opportunity

97 for behavioral flexibility, but often also the greater the cognitive challenge (Sambrook
98 & Whiten, 1997; Coolidge & Wynn, 2001). In humans, the selection and combination
99 of behaviors for a given task depends on factors such as the specific physical
100 components of the problem, the individual's level of expertise, and personal or
101 cultural preferences (Keen, 2011; MacDonald *et al.*, 2017). But, in addition to
102 choosing from within a repertoire of units, many behaviors also require multiple steps
103 that need to be executed in a particular order to be successful (Parker & Gibson,
104 1977; Sellet, 1993; Byrne *et al.*, 2001; Byrne, 2002; Fragaszy *et al.*, 2023; Wimpenny
105 *et al.*, 2009). As a result, where there are sequences of steps, another way in which
106 individuals may respond to a task with behavioral flexibility is by varying the order
107 and structure in which they complete these steps. These steps can be described
108 together as a behavioral '*program*' of actions (Byrne & Russon, 1998; Haidle, 2010).
109 If the *repertoire* of units is like an ingredients list of action items, the *program* is the
110 recipe, i.e. how they are combined (Byrne & Russon, 1998). The collective structure
111 of the program, such as the ways in which the program is ordered and/or how steps
112 (or sections of steps) are repeated, etc., is its '*action-grammar*' (Payne & Green,
113 1986; Pastra & Aloimonos, 2012; Hayashi, 2015).

114 The human ability to stack components into recursive, hierarchically-
115 structured sequences is most richly expressed as syntax (or grammar) in language
116 (Fitch *et al.*, 2010; Hurford, 2011; Lashley, 1951; Pastra & Aloimonos, 2012; Stout &
117 Chaminade, 2012) and music (Fitch, 2013; Fitch & Martins, 2014). But a similar
118 ability to order and iterate steps can be seen across many tasks (or programs of
119 action), from boiling a kettle to driving a car (e.g., Ambrose, 2001). Non-human
120 animals are also capable of hierarchical organization, or action-grammars, in their
121 behavioral programs (Byrne & Russon, 1998; Bergman *et al.*, 2003; Suzuki *et al.*,

122 2006; Carvalho *et al.*, 2008; Haidle, 2010; Sainburg *et al.*, 2019; Mielke & Carvahalo,
123 2022; Howard-Spink *et al.*, 2024; Lameira *et al.*, 2024; Wimpenny *et al.*, 2009).
124 Where this order can be varied flexibly case-by-case, with the ability to execute later
125 steps depending on earlier choices, these programs have been suggested to
126 indicate mental organization and the ability to plan ahead (e.g., to retrieve the
127 targeted reward at Step 3, one must first not only complete Steps 1 and 2, but do so
128 in such a way that already anticipates the need for Step 3; Russon 1998; Stokes &
129 Byrne, 2001; Sanz & Morgan, 2013).

130 Typically, the greater the number of ‘steps’ in the *program*, or the longer the
131 delay before achieving the goal (or reward), the more tenuous the connection
132 between earlier steps and their eventual outcome, increasing the cognitive challenge
133 of planning how to obtain it. For example, the acquisition of a tool (often required
134 towards the beginning of a tool behavioral *program*) could occur once an individual
135 has already arrived at a food resource that requires a tool, but could also be
136 anticipated or even planned for prior to arrival, i.e. where an individual collects a tool
137 on the way to the food source (e.g., Boesch & Boesch, 1984; Almeida-Warren *et al.*,
138 2017). Arriving to a tool use location with a tool suggests that the individual has a
139 mental representation of their future-orientated behavior, including both the target
140 and the tool required to access it (Byrne *et al.*, 2013; Osvath & Martin-Ordas, 2014;
141 Musgrave *et al.*, 2024). The rules by which programs can be completed (the action
142 grammar)—for example the number of steps, whether steps are optional, and
143 whether steps or sections can be repeated—offer insight into the cognitive
144 challenges faced to reach a desired outcome.

145 As with describing behavior, the detail in which programs of actions are
146 described can impact the degree of variation found. One approach to describing

147 behavioral repertoires and programs of actions is to adopt a multi-level structure,
148 allowing researchers to pinpoint when and where variation arises. Whilst terminology
149 for these multi-level structures changes across the literature, we define three levels:
150 *Functional Behavioral Categories, Behaviors and Behavioral Elements* (Table 1).
151 Each Functional Behavioral Category can be achieved through a set of Behaviors
152 (Table 1). For example, the Functional Behavioral Category 'Acquire Tool', could be
153 performed by either collecting an existing tool or by creating a new one. These
154 Behaviors are further specified by combinations of Behavioral Elements (Table 1).
155 The Behavior 'create tool' could be completed in various ways, such as tearing parts
156 off the tool (*'stripping'*) or cleanly breaking parts of the material away (*'clipping'*).
157 Choices for behaviors (and their behavioral elements) may not be independent of
158 one another. For example, choice of a tool type may require the individual to select
159 particular grip(s) (e.g., a power grip, as used to hold a hammer, or a precision grip,
160 as with a pen), specific action(s) (e.g., clipping, tearing, picking, or pulling), and the
161 use of different body part(s) (e.g., hands, lips, or teeth).

162

163 When comparing tool use within and across species, the behavioral Elements
164 for grip and action have drawn particular interest, as few tool use tasks can be
165 completed without holding and moving the tool. The ubiquity of grip and action in tool
166 use behaviors makes them an important source of comparative data across
167 individuals, tool use tasks, and species. Some grips are functionally optimized for
168 particular tasks: e.g., a power grip (where the tool is held within a fist with the thumb
169 closed over the tool) is ideal for completing a pounding action as it offers the most
170 force (Sperling et al., 1993). Whereas tasks that require the use of fine motor skills
171 are most effectively achieved with a precision grip (Moore & Dalley, 2018).

172 Alongside descriptions of grip and action, hand preference when performing a
173 task is often used to assess and compare the level of dexterity and/or skill required
174 to perform manual actions across tasks or individuals. The consistent decision to use
175 one hand more frequently than the other, across events and locations, suggests that
176 an individual is sacrificing the opportunity to use either hand flexibly depending on
177 local circumstances (e.g., continuing to use their left hand when the location of their
178 grooming partner, or the location and shape of a tree hole they are extracting water
179 from, would sometimes favor the use of their right hand; Boesch, 1991). Increasing
180 specialization (or strength of preference), is taken to indicate that a task is more
181 difficult to perform (Boesch, 1991). For example, studies of hand preference by wild
182 apes have typically shown strong evidence for individual lateralization in tool use (i.e.
183 consistent right- or left-hand preference) but not in reaching and grooming (Boesch,
184 1991; McGrew & Marchant, 1993; Lonsdorf & Hopkins, 2005), indicating task-
185 specialization. Hand preferences are particularly strongly expressed in challenging
186 manual-tasks that require several years to master (Boesch, 1991), such as nut-
187 cracking (Boesch, 1991 Sugiyama *et al.*, 1993), and nettle-processing (Byrne &
188 Byrne, 1991), but in other manual tasks apes retain substantial flexibility (Marchant &
189 McGrew, 1998; McGrew & Marchant, 2001; e.g., in gesturing: Hopkins & Leavens,
190 1998; Hobaiter & Byrne, 2012; although cf., object-mediated interactions: Hobaiter &
191 Byrne, 2012; Forrester *et al.*, 2011).

192

193 **1.1 Exploring behavioral units and programs in chimpanzee algae fishing**

194 Chimpanzees are highly prolific tool users who demonstrate substantial
195 behavioral variation in the expression of a specific tool-task (e.g., when gathering
196 honey: Sanz & Morgan, 2009; Estienne *et al.*, 2019a; or when retrieving ants: Humle

197 & Matsuzawa, 2002). While the order of Functional Behavioral Categories tends to
198 remain relatively stable within a given tool-use context (e.g., Estienne *et al.*, 2019),
199 the specific Behaviors and Behavioral Elements employed can vary (Estienne *et al.*,
200 2019a; Humle & Matsuzawa, 2002; Boesch *et al.*, 2020), with systematic differences
201 observed both within and between communities (Boesch *et al.*, 2020).

202 Algae fishing is a recently documented chimpanzee tool use behavior
203 (Boesch *et al.*, 2017), that offers substantial potential for within-task behavioral
204 variation. Indications of the cognitive challenge algae fishing may pose are evident in
205 the initial description of algae fishing, where Boesch and colleagues (2017) report
206 consistency of hand use within a fishing event and preliminary evidence suggesting
207 population right-handedness. Although a relatively rare food source in chimpanzee
208 diets, algae consumption has been reported in a handful of populations as a food
209 item that is collected directly using the hands (Sakamaki, 1998; Devos *et al.*, 2002;
210 Bueno de Mesquita *et al.*, 2021), or using short (~0.5m) plant tools to skim algae
211 from the surface of the water (termed '*algae scooping*': Matsuzawa *et al.*, 1996;
212 Matsuzawa, 2019; Devos *et al.*, 2002). In contrast, algae *fishing* involves the use of
213 variably sized stick tools up to 4m in length, to retrieve sub-surface algae growing
214 from the substrate in, at times, deep water (Boesch *et al.*, 2017). While algae
215 scooping tools have been described in detail (Humle *et al.* 2011), the tool use
216 behavior itself is described more generally and, beyond growing from the surface (in
217 scooping) or substrate (in fishing), there is no further information on the types of
218 algae fished for. We focus on a detailed description of the behavioral repertoire of
219 algae fishing in the same population of chimpanzees studied by Boesch *et al* (2017),
220 with the hope that this work facilitates comparison across examples of tool-based
221 algae consumption and other extractive-foraging behavior.

222 Recognizing the importance of a structured systematic approach to behavioral
223 descriptions and the potential for behavioral variation while algae fishing, we build on
224 Boesch and colleagues' (2017) initial report by developing a systematic, detailed
225 behavioral repertoire for algae fishing, including a description of the behavioral steps
226 at three levels of granularity: Functional Behavioral Categories, Behaviors, and
227 Behavioral Elements (following Sanz & Morgan, 2009; see Table 1, Figure S1). We
228 then applied this repertoire to define an algae fishing program and its accompanying
229 action-grammar: the structure and order of behavioral steps when fishing. By
230 describing algae fishing at these structured levels of detail, we offer a framework for
231 behavioral description and facilitate comparison between algae fishing and other tool
232 use tasks across populations and species. We show how both the size of the
233 repertoire and our perceived flexibility of its use can depend upon the levels of
234 descriptive detail applied. We do so in the structure of the behavioral program, and in
235 the selection and combination of Behavioral Elements while preparing to fish, while
236 fishing, and while retrieving algae.

237

238 **2. METHODS**

239 **2.1 Ethics statement**

240 Ethical approval to collect the data used within this study was granted by the Animal
241 Ethics and Welfare Committee of the University of St Andrews (reference: PS15842;
242 and PS15893). Research was carried out with the permission of the Guinean
243 Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur de la Recherche Scientifique et de
244 l'Innovation and the Office Guinéen des Parcs Nationaux et Réserves de Faune. All
245 research was conducted following the legal requirements of the Republic of Guinea

246 and the United Kingdom. All research adhered to the American Society of
247 Primatologists Principles for the Ethical Treatment of Non-Human Primates.

248

249 **2.2 Study site and subjects**

250 Data were collected at the Moyen-Bafing Chimpanzee Project (MBCP). Located in
251 the former Bakoun Classified Forest of the Moyen-Bafing National Park in Guinea
252 (11.7267° N -12.7558° W), the MBCP research area (~220km²) encompasses a
253 savanna-mosaic ecosystem and contains an estimated minimum of ~227 western
254 chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes verus*; Debetencourt *et al.*, 2024). Algae fishing
255 mainly occurs during October to July and since February 2022, has been
256 opportunistically recorded by the MBCP using camera traps (Bushnell DS-4K No
257 Glow) and indirect surveys.

258

259 **2.3 Video coding**

260 Algae fishing occurs at pools of water that are freely accessible in the
261 landscape (i.e. no digging or modification of the environment is required to access
262 the water). We define a 'pool' as a body of water often demarcated by the natural
263 features of winding waterways, such as a combination of large boulders, natural
264 ridges, changes in channel depth, vegetated banks, or accumulation of leaf litter. All
265 pools included in these analyses were separated by a minimum of 5m distance. As
266 many tool use behaviors develop over ontogeny with learning extending into
267 adolescence, we limited the dataset for analysis to adults (15+ years; Goodall,
268 1986), which biases our description to be more conservative as it is less likely to
269 include non-functional elements. Adults would be expected to be proficient tool users
270 who are more likely to show minimal variation as a result of early trial-and-error

271 learning. When describing the algae fishing ethogram, we do so at three nested
272 levels of temporal specificity: a '*Session*', which is made up of one or more
273 '*Sequences*', which is, in turn, made up of one or more '*Dips*' (see Table 2). A
274 Session captures the entirety of that instance of tool behavior, a Sequence captures
275 the process to each successful outcome (e.g., eating), and a Dip captures each
276 unique action (or attempt) at retrieving the item. These levels can be generalized to
277 other tool use behavior.

278

279 As the MBCP video library is large (> 7300 one-minute chimpanzee videos,
280 February 2022 to March 2023), behavioral coding for all examples of algae fishing
281 was not feasible. Therefore, we subsampled the MBCP video library available at the
282 onset of video coding (March 2023), which comprised two algae fishing seasons
283 (recordings from February 2022 to May 2022 and November 2022 to March 2023.
284 When selecting videos for coding, we endeavored to balance the dataset across
285 individuals and locations. Video data were organized by watercourse (i.e. the larger
286 body of running water along which pools were located) and, within each
287 watercourse, by camera trap location (the position of the camera trap), and date of
288 recording. Each camera trap location-date combination was assigned a unique
289 number, and a subset of video data were randomly selected for subsequent
290 behavioral coding using a random number generator. Within each location-date
291 dataset, all videos were searched in chronological order for algae fishing. When a
292 video contained algae fishing in which at least one complete Dip by an adult could be
293 coded, we checked the identity of the individual fishing and the number of Dips
294 already coded for that individual. Dips within these videos were then coded unless
295 the individual's contribution to the dataset would exceed 25% of the total number of

296 Dips coded for that watercourse (at the time of coding), in which case that individual
297 was skipped. (In practice, this only occurred for one individual.) Our final coded
298 dataset included 30 camera trap locations distributed across 21 pools, including 62
299 adult chimpanzees.

300 For an individual fishing, we coded: date, time, location, session length,
301 individual identity, sex, tool acquisition, tool properties, number of tools used, and the
302 number of other individuals present. A full protocol for behavioral coding, including all
303 variables and definitions is provided in the SI. Coding of an individual fishing
304 continued across all videos to complete the algae fishing Session (Table 2). We
305 considered a new Session to start if there was a pause of 30-seconds or longer
306 between any of the coded behavioral elements for algae fishing at the same location.
307 Time-based thresholds when defining a behavior offer a replicable means to
308 describe data, but can also be subjective where there are insufficient data to (as yet)
309 justify their duration through, for example, natural break analysis (Bivand, 2022). In
310 this case, we only needed to apply a time-based threshold to <1% (1 of 181
311 Sessions) of the dataset, and so even if 30-seconds is not reflective of differentiated
312 breaks between 'true' sessions, the application of this cut off here is unlikely to have
313 introduced substantial bias as it so rarely occurred. When a video contained multiple
314 adult individuals fishing, all eligible (i.e. adult) individuals were coded. Alongside the
315 capping of individuals, data coding was also capped so that data from a single algae
316 fishing season did not represent more than 75% of the total dataset for that
317 watercourse.

318 We consider potential sources of bias in our sample using the STRANGE
319 framework (Webster & Rutz, 2020), with a detailed description available in the SI. In
320 particular, we describe the possible impacts of using camera trap video data, of an

321 individual's experience on behavioral expression, and of competition in territorial
322 boundary areas on potential inferences drawn about this behavior.

323

324 **2.4 Establishing a behavioral ethogram for algae fishing**

325 Like all great apes, chimpanzees also show substantial fine motor control
326 relative to that of other primates (Hopkins & Pilcher, 2001; Barton & Venditti, 2014;
327 Verendeev *et al.*, 2016), with widespread evidence for a strong selective pressure on
328 apes' range of movement and precision in hands and forelimbs (Temerin, 1983;
329 Isler, 2005; Hunt, 2016; Verendeev *et al.*, 2016; Fannin *et al.*, 2023). Chimpanzees
330 show a similar range of manual motor-control to humans and employ a similar range
331 of tool-grips (although their notably shorter thumbs mean that pinch grips are more
332 often expressed between two fingers than finger and thumb (Marzke, 1997; Almécija
333 *et al.*, 2015)), with grip choice and proficiency developing with age (Estienne *et al.*,
334 2019; Malherbe *et al.*, 2024).

335 We defined the algae fishing ethogram by building on existing extractive
336 foraging frameworks and definitions in apes (Byrne *et al.*, 2001; Boesch & Boesch,
337 1990; Boesch *et al.*, 2009; Sanz & Morgan, 2009; McGrew, 1974). For variants in
338 behavior that did not conform to existing descriptions and were observed on more
339 than one occasion, we created new definitions and added these definitions to the
340 ethogram. In general, we adopted a bottom-up approach: coding in as much detail
341 as possible, allowing us to subsequently define categories at different levels of
342 granularity. For example, we discriminated Swivel-inwards, Swivel-outwards, and
343 Swivel-unclear (where the Action was clearly a Swivel but the direction of motion
344 under the water could not be reliably discriminated). We could have assigned Swivel-
345 unclear Actions to a larger 'Unknown' Action category; however, by specifying the

346 information available, this approach to coding allows the observer to retain the option
347 of ‘lumping’ up data to a higher-order category (e.g., here: Swivel) for potential
348 analysis, minimizing potential data losses.

349 We assessed the completeness of our description of the behavioral
350 repertoires for two widely described Behaviors (Grip and Action) and their
351 combination into Techniques through asymptote curves. The number of elements in
352 repertoires for each of the Behaviors (Grip, Action) and their combination
353 (Technique) were plotted against the number of observations (Dips) to visualize
354 when in the coding effort new elements were first described.

355

356 **2.5 Dataset used to establish behavioral ethogram**

357 In total, we coded 1068 minutes of algae fishing from 608 videos (note that some
358 videos included multiple individuals fishing), which comprised $n = 181$ Sessions, $n =$
359 2140 Sequences, and $n = 2431$ Dips (see Table 2), from 36 adult males and 26 adult
360 females across the 21 pools (for details of data distribution see Table S1). Within the
361 dataset, each individual contributed a mean of 2.89 Sessions (± 3.81 [SD], range: 1-
362 27) and each pool had a mean of 8.48 Sessions recorded at it (± 8.33 [SD], range: 1-
363 39). We do not include or discuss the potential impact of community identity on
364 behavior as we cannot reliably assign all individuals in our dataset to specific
365 communities, especially since some pools occur in areas used by more than one
366 community (Debetencourt *et al.*, 2024).

367 To test observer reliability of the coding completed by CW, CH re-coded a
368 subset of dips ($n=144$ from $n=34$ Sessions), representing ~6% of the dataset. We
369 calculated both percentage agreement between raters and Cohen’s Kappa (κ) on 12
370 variables (Table S2; a weighted value was used for ordinal variables). Agreement

371 was only marked where both coders indicated the same classification for a variable
372 (e.g. Grip = Power). Data points in which classification of a variable was marked as
373 'Unknown' (e.g., Grip = Unknown) by one rater, were treated as a case of
374 disagreement. Agreement on all variables was above 0.81 κ , which is classified as
375 'almost perfect' (Landis & Koch, 1977), with all percentage agreements between 88-
376 99%.

377

378 2.5.1 *Hand preferences*

379 Hand preferences have been described across a wide variety of manual tasks
380 (Boesch, 1991; Marchant & McGrew, 1998; McGrew & Marchant, 2001; Hopkins &
381 Leavens, 1998; Hobaiter & Byrne, 2012; Forrester *et al.*, 2011) and have been used
382 as a means to compare potential task difficulty (via measures of preference strength,
383 e.g., Boesch, 1991). To measure the direction of hand preference while algae
384 fishing, we subset the data to individuals with five or more Sessions with Dips of
385 observable hand-use and used a hand preference index (HI), calculated as $(R-L)/N$.
386 The index varies between -1 and 1, with -1 indicating complete left-hand use, and 1
387 indicating complete right-hand use. Note that no individual was observed to use both
388 hands to perform a fishing Action within a single Dip. We calculated an HI score for
389 per Session per individual. We used these scores to i) calculate strength within a
390 Session for each individual, and ii) to calculate a mean HI score per individual across
391 their fishing Sessions. To measure the strength of hand preference, independently of
392 direction, we calculated an Absolute Hand Preference index (ABS HI), as ABS
393 $HI = \sqrt{(HI^2)}$, which varies from 0 (no preference) to 1 (complete hand preference in
394 either direction). We calculated an individual's ABS HI across Sessions.

395 We also calculated an individual's ABS HI score for three of the five Actions
396 (Dunk, Swivel-inwards, Swivel-outwards) where an individual had at least 5 Dips with
397 observable body part for that Action ($n = 1444$, $n = 36$ individuals; two actions Sway
398 and Flick were excluded as there were too few individuals with $n = 5$ Dips for each of
399 these Actions, $n = 1$ and $n = 0$ individuals respectively), and then used these to
400 describe the distribution of ABS HI scores for individual Actions, providing a measure
401 of the flexibility in hand use within each Action. For a full description of the Actions
402 see Table 4 and Figure 3 in Results).

403

404

405 **3. RESULTS**

406 **3.1 The behavioral repertoire and action-grammar of algae fishing**

407 We coded 2431 algae fishing Dips, from 62 adult individuals, across 21 pools.
408 Adult fishing Sessions contained a range of 1-119 Sequences ($\bar{x} = 12 \pm 18$ [SD]
409 Sequences) and lasted between 7 to 3427 seconds ($\bar{x} = 357 \pm 487$ seconds). Most
410 Dips were successful, with algae retrieved in 77% of Dips ($n = 1866$ of 2431 Dips).
411 Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees employed a diverse repertoire of behavioral units when
412 algae fishing, including: eight Functional Behavioral Categories, and 21 Behaviors
413 produced using 64 Behavioral Elements (see Table 3; Table 4).

414

415 *3.1.1 LEVEL 1: Functional Behavioral Categories*

416 Algae fishing Sessions contained up to eight Functional Behavioral
417 Categories, with 'Find Algae' and 'Remove Debris' as optional steps. The order of
418 the Functional Behavioral Categories was fixed by the functional requirements of the
419 behavior (e.g., it is impossible to eat algae before first retrieving it). However,

420 chimpanzees demonstrated flexibility in their algae fishing program in two ways: in
421 the presence or absence of steps, and in iterations (repetitions) of steps (Figure 1).
422 Dips were repeated within a Sequence, but rarely (n = 182 of 2140 Sequences,
423 <1%); whereas Sequences were repeated frequently (n = 163 of 181 Sessions,
424 90%), and up to 119 times within a Session. The modal Functional Behavioral
425 Category action-pattern within a Session was: acquire tool—prepare to fish—
426 complete 11 Sequences (each with a single Dip)—discard tool (Figure 1).

427

428 *3.1.2 LEVEL 2: Behaviors*

429 A repertoire of 21 Behaviors was available to complete a Session (Table 3).
430 While the inclusion and ordering of the Functional Behavioral Categories was
431 relatively fixed during algae fishing, the inclusion and ordering of Behaviors (collect
432 tool, create tool, adjust tool) within them were more flexible. Some Behaviors (n = 7,
433 Table 3) were performed in every case of successful algae retrieval, and are classed
434 as 'required' (e.g., Grip and Action, as it is impossible to fish for algae with a tool
435 without holding and moving it), whilst other Behaviors (n = 14, Table 3) were
436 'optional' in the sense that they were not consistently performed (e.g., Inspect Water,
437 or Clear Debris).

438

439 *3.1.3 LEVEL 3: Behavioral Elements*

440 The size of the repertoire used during algae fishing increased substantially
441 when considering the Behavioral Elements from which an individual could choose to
442 complete a Behavior. Each Behavior was produced by using a choice of up to eight
443 Behavioral Element(s) (range: 1-8; $\bar{x} = 3 \pm 2$ SD).

444 All required Behaviors included multiple Behavioral Elements (for example:
445 Grip, see Table 4). The 14 optional Behaviors were either produced using a single
446 Behavioral Element (n = 6 of 14), or by choosing from among multiple Behavioral
447 Elements (n = 8 of 14; e.g., adjust tool could be completed with either 'strip' or 'clip').
448

449 **3.2 Grips**

450 We provide a detailed description of the Grips and Actions used in algae fishing, to
451 both understand how algae fishing is executed and to facilitate comparisons with
452 other tool use contexts. The Behavioral Elements described for Grip reached
453 asymptote after only 16% of data coded; n=306 Dips), suggesting that our analysis
454 fully captured the behavioral diversity expressed by the Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees
455 (Fig 4). Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees employed five distinct Grips when fishing for
456 algae (Figure 2, Table 4). Within a Session, individuals used up to four Grip types,
457 although the most commonly observed (i.e. mode) number of Grip types per Session
458 was one.

459 Adult individuals used predominantly three Grips (mode = 3; across
460 Sessions). Of the 47 adult chimpanzees with more than five Dips recorded with
461 observable Grips, two individuals used all five observed Grips, six used four Grips,
462 17 used three Grips, 22 used two Grips, and 11 were observed to use one Grip.
463 However, the number of Grips recorded for an individual correlated with the quantity
464 of data recorded for that individual (Pearson's correlation test: $t = 2.1$, $df = 45$, $p =$
465 0.04), and all individuals observed using only one Grip had fewer than 50 Dips coded
466 in our dataset, suggesting that data density influenced the likelihood of a Grip
467 Behavioral Element being recorded in an individual's repertoire.

468

469

470

471

472 3.3. Actions

473 The Behavioral Elements described for Action reached asymptote after ~6% of data

474 coded, suggesting full behavioral diversity was captured (Fig 4). Moyen-Bafing

475 chimpanzees used four distinct Actions when fishing for algae. Within a Session,

476 chimpanzees were found to use up to four Actions, but the modal number of Actions

477 used was one.

478 Adult individuals used a modal two Actions (across Sessions). Of the 46 adult

479 chimpanzees with more than five Dips recorded with observable Actions, six

480 individuals used all available Actions, 12 used three Actions, 20 used two Actions

481 and eight chimpanzees were observed to use one Action. However, as for Grips, the

482 number of Behavioral Elements for Action recorded for an individual correlated with

483 the quantity of data recorded for that individual (Pearsons's correlation test: $t = 2.4$,

484 $df = 44$, $p = 0.02$), and all individuals observed using only one Action had fewer than

485 50 Dips coded, suggesting that data density also influenced the likelihood of an

486 Action Behavioral Element being recorded in an individual's repertoire.

487

488 3.4 Flexibility in the selection of Behavioral Elements

489 In our dataset, chimpanzees used 1,468 unique sequences of Behavioral

490 Elements. Successful dips (for which at least 50% of the dip's information could be

491 reliably coded; without unknowns) contained an average of 11 unique Behavioral

492 Elements (± 2 SD, range 4-15). Individuals (with more than 5 dips recorded) used an

493 average of 25 unique Behavioral Elements (± 8 SD; range: 9 - 44; theoretical

494 maximum; 64). However, the number of Behavioral Elements recorded for an

495 individual correlated with the quantity of data recorded for that individual (Pearsons's
496 correlation test: $t = 6.1$, $df = 40$, $p < 0.01$).

497

498 **3.5 Flexibility while Preparing to Fish**

499 In addition to the execution of multi-step programs of actions, two Functional
500 Behavioral Categories provided indications of behavior consistent with preparedness
501 at the level of the Session. Chimpanzees arrived in view of the camera at the algae
502 fishing location with a tool already in hand (Arrive with tool) on 66% of Sessions ($n =$
503 99 of 151) where tool acquisition could be coded ($n = 97$ Sessions with one tool; $n =$
504 2 Sessions with multiple tools). Chimpanzees also left the field of view with their tool
505 in hand (Carry tool away) when finishing their Session in 43% of Sessions ($n = 66$ of
506 152 sessions where the destination of the tool at the end of a Session could be
507 observed).

508 Chimpanzees fished from a variety of positions, but most commonly stood
509 with three limbs on the ground ($n = 1231$ Sequences). Chimpanzees occasionally
510 used plants or rocks to hang from ($n = 178$ Sequences), and fished from a
511 combination of places (e.g., arms in the water and legs on ground: $n = 220$
512 Sequences). Changing fishing position within a Session ($n = 82$ of 181 Sessions,
513 33%) was relatively common.

514

515 **3.6 Flexibility while Fishing**

516 When fishing, chimpanzees cleared debris from the surface of the water on
517 3% of occasions ($n = 50$ of 1995 Sequences where we could see if they cleared
518 debris), and head bopped (Table 4; chimpanzee moves head back and forth, or up

519 and down in a repetitive motion whilst looking at the water) on 18% of occasions (n =
520 342 of 1891 Sequences where the head was visible).

521 When Dips within a Sequence were repeated, the Dip could be completed
522 using the same Behavioral Element(s) as in the previous Dip or could offer an
523 opportunity for adjustment. We specifically investigated adjustment in the Behavioral
524 Elements for the combination of two Behavior (Grip and Action) as a Technique.
525 Adjustment of Technique within a Dip (i.e. changing Grip or Action while the tool
526 remained submerged in the water) was very rare (n = 26 of 2431 Dips, <1%).
527 Adjustment of Technique between Dips within a Sequence also occurred very rarely
528 (n = 59 of 1207 Sequences where Technique could be coded across the entire
529 Sequence, <1%). In contrast, adjustment of Technique was frequently observed
530 across Sequences within a fishing Session (n= 102 of 157 Sessions for which
531 Technique could be coded across the entire Session; 65%).

532

533 *3.6.1 Strength and direction of hand preferences while fishing*

534 Individual chimpanzees were strongly lateralized within a session, exhibiting a
535 consistent hand preference (n=8 individuals; ABS HI: range = 0.67-1.00, \bar{x} = 0.99
536 \pm 0.04 SD), but did not show a consistent direction of hand preference across
537 Sessions (HI: range = -1.00-1.00, \bar{x} = 0.02 \pm 1.00 SD; Fig.5A).

538 We found minor variation between the Actions in the consistency of an
539 individual's hand preference when performing an Action. Overall, most individuals
540 used the same hand to perform the same Action. However, individuals showed a
541 slightly larger absolute hand preference for the Action Swivel-inwards (n = 2 ABS HI
542 range 0.33-0.85; n = 6 ABS HI = 1.0) as compared to the Actions Dunk (n = 6 ABS
543 HI: range 0.07-0.79; n = 9 ABS HI = 1.0), and Swivel-outwards (n = 13 ABS HI range

544 0.06-0.94; $n = 19$ ABS HI = 1.0; Fig. 5B). With the mean ABS-HI values for Swivel-in
545 (ABS HI $\bar{x} = 0.90 \pm 0.23$ SD), also slightly higher across individuals than Swivel-out
546 (ABS HI $\bar{x} = 0.82 \pm 0.30$ SD), and Dunk (ABS HI $\bar{x} = 0.81 \pm 0.29$ SD).

547

548 **3.7 Flexibility while Retrieving Algae**

549 Chimpanzees used their hands, feet, mouth, and arms to bring the tool back towards
550 themselves during algae retrieval. It was more common during retrieval Actions for
551 chimpanzees to use multiple body parts than it was to use multiple body parts during
552 fishing ($n = 360$ of 1848 Sequences with observable retrieval Actions; 19.5%; Chi-
553 square test: $\chi^2 = 380.95$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$).

554 When retrieving algae, the most common Action was to bring the end of the
555 tool straight to the mouth ($n = 1372$ of 1856 Sequences with observable retrieval
556 Actions; 73.9%). Chimpanzees used both their hands and their mouths to remove
557 algae from the end of the tool, typically by swiping the tool through their mouth or
558 hand ($n = 1606$ of 1859 Sequences with observable eating Actions; 86.4%) rather
559 than by picking algae off the tool with their mouth or hand ($n = 253$ of 1859
560 Sequences with observable eating Actions; 13.6%; Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 1730.9$, $df =$
561 1 , $p\text{-value} < 0.01$). Chimpanzees also occasionally removed debris from algae they
562 retrieved while eating it ($n = 50$ of 1995 Sequences where this could be reliably
563 coded; 2.5%).

564 4. DISCUSSION

565 Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees employ a varied repertoire of behavioral units when
566 fishing for algae: eight Functional Behavioral Categories and 21 Behaviors, produced
567 using 64 Behavioral Elements. The order of the program of actions was largely fixed
568 at the highest-level of categorization (i.e. Functional Behavioral Categories) but,
569 even at this hierarchical level, algae fishing in this population included two optional
570 steps leading to four main variations in the observed program of actions, with further
571 variation generated by the use of iterations (i.e. repetitions of both individual
572 Functional Behavioral Categories and sets of multiple Functional Behavioral
573 Categories). At the level of Behaviors, the number of program variations generated
574 by the combination of units was orders of magnitude larger. As in other tool use
575 behavior, chimpanzees employed a set of different Grips. However, unlike most
576 other tool tasks (Sanz & Morgan, 2010; e.g., nut cracking with stone tools: Biro *et al.*,
577 2006; leaf-folding for drinking water: Tonooka, 2001), adult chimpanzees retained
578 and used a variety of Actions when fishing for algae, suggesting that there is unlikely
579 to be a single 'optimal' solution across individuals and occasions in this dynamic
580 problem space.

581 Comparison across types of tool use—even within chimpanzees, let alone
582 across species—is made challenging where the frameworks used to describe
583 behavioral variation vary in specificity and completeness (Estienne *et al.*, 2017;
584 Grund *et al.*, 2024). Here we provide a framework to facilitate comparison, by
585 incorporating features of tool use description from across studies (Byrne *et al.*, 2001;
586 Boesch & Boesch, 1990; Boesch *et al.*, 2009; Sanz & Morgan, 2009; McGrew, 1974;
587 Estienne *et al.*, 2017) and using these as a basis to systematically describe a new
588 tool behavior at multiple levels of detail. In doing so, we not only characterize a new

589 tool behavior in detail, but we provide a basis from which to start to quantify variation
590 in this behavior (algae fishing) relative to that reported for other chimpanzee tool
591 tasks.

592 For example, in a study of underground honey extraction, Estienne and
593 colleagues (2017) identify three Phases (exploration, tool manufacture, extraction)
594 and 14-17 Behaviors (termed Actions) which include a combination of what we term
595 Behavior and Behavioral Elements (Table 5). They estimate that Action repertoire
596 size in other studies of tool use varied from 2 to 13 of their Actions (including leaf
597 sponging, underground and arboreal honey extraction, nut cracking, and elevated
598 and subterranean termite fishing; Estienne *et al.*, 2017; Tonooka, 2001; Sanz &
599 Morgan, 2010; Sousa *et al.*, 2009; Inoue-Nakamura & Matsuzawa, 1997; Nishida &
600 Hiraiwa, 1982, Table 5). In comparison, algae fishing appears to offer substantial
601 potential for behavioral variation, with large repertoires of units at all levels of
602 granularity, and a relatively long program (cf., other tool uses: Estienne *et al.*, 2017;
603 Sanz & Morgan, 2010; Lonsdorf, 2005; Biro *et al.*, 2006; Boesch *et al.*, 2020, Table
604 5).

605

606 While there is no objectively ‘correct’ level of analysis—these are sensitive to
607 the question being asked (and the data available)—the use of fine-grained and
608 consistently structured descriptions of behavior allows for easier comparison across
609 studies (as units of analysis can be reconstituted or ‘translated’ across samples;
610 Grund *et al.*, 2024; Mielke *et al.*, 2024). Chimpanzee algae fishing can, at one level
611 of description, have relatively little variation (with flexibility limited to omissions or
612 repetitions) and, simultaneously, thousands of program variants at other levels of
613 description (where dozens of different Behavioral Elements are selected from to

614 complete a Behavior). The systematic inclusion of essential Behaviors (for example
615 in tool use: Grip, Action, and their combination as Technique) at the same level of
616 detail (Behavioral Elements) across studies could provide a key foundation in which
617 to situate the relative flexibility of a behavior within and across species (Wessling *et*
618 *al.*, 2025b). Moreover, systematic descriptions are also important for accurate
619 comparisons in applied conservation actions: for example, in understanding
620 population resilience in the face of rapid environmental change, or in defining target
621 populations for conservation activities (Wessling & Surbeck, 2022; Wessling *et al.*,
622 2025a).

623 Regular within-individual adjustment of Techniques within an algae fishing
624 Session suggests that chimpanzees can respond dynamically within an algae fishing
625 event (for example, as the availability of algae in a location diminishes). By contrast,
626 comparable flexibility in Technique was not seen at the level of a Dip or Sequence.
627 Similarly, planning to bring a tool with you (or take it on afterwards), could only be
628 observed at the level of a Session. Other types of behavioral flexibility can be
629 detected at the level of Sequences. For example, chimpanzees regularly
630 incorporated Behaviors such as clearing the surface of the water or head bopping
631 movements, likely in response to the challenges of an aquatic niche such as surface
632 obstructions, or visual challenges of diffraction and sun glitter (Loew & McFarland,
633 1990; Temple *et al.*, 2010).

634 The problem being solved when fishing for algae changes both across pools
635 and within pools over time. Across Sessions, pool depth, water opacity, water current
636 strength, algae growth depth, algae density, access to the pool, and the social
637 environment, among others, can change. Within a Session, algae growth depth,
638 algae density, access to the pool and the social environment can change. To be able

639 to successfully acquire algae, chimpanzees must navigate a dynamic problem space
640 by selecting and executing the appropriate combination and sequence of Behavioral
641 Elements—choices that appear particularly extensive for algae fishing (Table 4), as
642 compared to those made in other tasks, given their repertoire sizes and program
643 lengths (Estienne *et al.*, 2017; Sanz & Morgan, 2010; Lonsdorf, 2005; Biro *et al.*,
644 2006; Boesch *et al.*, 2020; Table 5). If each choice represents a distinct decision
645 step that must be integrated into a single outcome, it would suggest that algae
646 fishing is a cognitively demanding task. While the population repertoire comprises
647 thousands of *program* variants, real-time decision-making is shaped by immediate
648 circumstances, and—at any one time—many of these variants may be unavailable
649 (e.g., some spots from which to fish around the pool may be already occupied, or
650 debris may only need cleared on the first, but not subsequent, Sequences). These
651 contextual constraints likely simplify the load on working memory and decision
652 making, thereby moderating the overall cognitive challenge. Although algae fishing
653 has, at present, only been described in Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees, ‘algae scooping’
654 is present at other chimpanzee communities (Matsuzawa *et al.*, 1996; Matsuzawa,
655 2019; Devos *et al.*, 2002). Algae scooping involves collecting algae from the water’s
656 surface using small stick tools (Matsuzawa *et al.*, 1996; Matsuzawa, 2019; Devos *et al.*
657 *et al.*, 2002). While algae fishing and algae scooping address a similar general problem
658 (ie using tools to obtain algae) and may constitute a continuum rather than a strict
659 dichotomy, algae fishing likely involves greater variability due to the wider range of
660 tool lengths and water depths involved. A systematic description of algae scooping
661 within a comparable framework will allow us to investigate if, where, and how these
662 behaviors differ.

663 For two of the most widely described aspects of tool-use: Grip and Action, and
664 their combination into 22 algae fishing Techniques, the repertoires of units used in
665 algae fishing quickly reached an asymptote at the population level. That Techniques
666 quickly reached asymptote suggests that, at our most fine-grained level of
667 description (Behavioral Elements), the full extent of variation in the repertoire was
668 sufficiently/reliably captured. While we described variation between individuals in
669 their repertoire size, these differences appeared very sensitive to sample size,
670 suggesting that further data collection per individual would likely result in more, if not
671 all, the population-level Behavioral Elements being described in their individual
672 repertoire. As a result, individual variation in the use of Grips, Actions, and
673 Techniques likely reflects flexible, case-by-case responses to specific challenges—
674 shaped by the physical and social environment or by personal preferences—rather
675 than an inability to perform particular behaviors. Most examples of chimpanzee tool
676 use appear to have a clear optimal Action on which individuals converge (Sanz &
677 Morgan, 2010; e.g., nut cracking with stone tools: Biro *et al.*, 2006; leaf-folding for
678 drinking water: Tonooka, 2001). In contrast, chimpanzees' exploitation of their large
679 repertoire of Actions in algae fishing supports the possibility that chimpanzees may
680 benefit from retaining flexibility in this dynamic problem space.

681 One means to assess the physical and cognitive challenge of producing
682 manual actions is the extent to which individuals show specialization through
683 stronger hand preferences (rather than retaining the flexibility to use either hand in
684 response to variation in the physical environment; Leavens *et al.*, 2001; Fitch &
685 Braccini, 2013; Boesch, 1991), with hand specialization suggested to benefit
686 efficiency (McGrew & Marchant, 1999). Our findings support Boesch and colleagues'
687 (2017) report that individual chimpanzees were near-perfectly lateralized when

688 fishing for algae (i.e. they do not swap hands during a Session). In this respect,
689 individuals show comparatively strong hand preferences when algae fishing, similar
690 to those reported for other cognitively challenging tool-tasks such as nut cracking
691 with paired stone tools (Bossou: ABS-HI = 1.0, Humle & Matsuzawa, 2009), and as
692 high or higher (ABS-HI = 0.7-1.0) than those reported for a range of tool-task
693 behavior (ABS-HI = 0.5-0.8; Humle & Matsuzawa, 2009).

694 However, we do not find evidence of population-level right handedness. In
695 part, this discrepancy could be explained by our focus on adults: a previously
696 reported right-handed bias was most prominent in immature individuals, with no
697 evidence for a bias in adults (Boesch et al., 2017). We find that across Sessions,
698 only half of the individuals could be described as demonstrating a strong hand
699 preference, and only one of eight was right-hand biased. Our data meet, at most,
700 Level 2 (of a possible 5) in McGrew and Marchant's (2001) framework for population-
701 level laterality (with humans at Level 5; McGrew & Marchant, 2001). Chimpanzees'
702 choice of left or right hand when fishing for algae may be shaped, in part, by the
703 physical affordances of the local environment. Environmental constraints may limit
704 the ability to maintain a hand preference whilst using tools, as found for other
705 behavior, such as ant fishing (Marchant & McGrew, 2007). We also found some
706 consistency in an individual's hand preference when performing a particular fishing
707 Action, across different Sessions most individuals preferred to use the same hand to
708 produce the same Action, with the greatest consistency in Swivel-inwards Actions.
709 Together these findings suggest that there may be some benefits from task
710 specialization in algae fishing—but that these operate most strongly at the level of
711 specific Behavioral Elements, and that individuals retain the ability to produce even
712 fine-grained motor skills with either hand when needed.

713 Finally, Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees typically (66%) arrived in view with a tool
714 already in hand. Algae fishing tools can be over 4m in length (Boesch *et al.*, 2017),
715 and while bamboo and wood may be relatively lightweight materials, longer tools are
716 likely inconvenient to carry. The use of camera trap data means that we cannot
717 assess the distance across which the chimpanzees were transporting their tools, and
718 these cases could reflect relatively minor adjustments in position around a pool or
719 the sourcing of the tool from a nearby plant in view of the pool. Most camera trap
720 models have a trigger distance of under 40m making this type of data collection not
721 well suited to assessing whether chimpanzees carry their tools across longer
722 distances. However, at other sites chimpanzees have been observed carrying tools
723 over dozens of meters suggesting that they are indeed out-of-sight of the problem
724 when gathering tool material (nut-cracking in Tai Forest: Boesch & Boesch, 1984;
725 termite-fishing in Issa: Almeida-Warren *et al.*, 2017), and that chimpanzees have a
726 mental representation of the problem they are planning to solve (Boesch & Boesch,
727 1984; Byrne *et al.*, 2013; Almeida-Warren *et al.*, 2017; Musgrave *et al.*, 2024).

728

729 **5. CONCLUSION**

730 The relatively large repertoires of Behaviors and Behavioral Elements described of
731 this behavior, alongside their hierarchical organization in a program of actions that
732 shows variation in structure, supports the body of evidence that chimpanzees respond
733 flexibly to cognitively challenging tasks (Sambrook & Whiten, 1997; Coolidge & Wynn,
734 2001). Our ability to situate the relative behavioral flexibility shown in a task, or within
735 and between species, remains limited by differences in the ways in which behavior are
736 described, with important implications for our ability to address questions relating to

737 cognitive and behavioral evolution and adaptability. Here, we provide a systematic
738 description of a new tool task in chimpanzees at multiple levels of detail. In doing so
739 we facilitate comparison with other tool tasks and show that adult chimpanzees
740 continue to use a particularly diverse set of Techniques when fishing for algae,
741 suggesting that they benefit from retaining multiple solutions in this dynamic problem
742 space.

743

744

745 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

746 We thank the Office Guinéen des Parcs Nationaux et Réserves de Faune, and the
747 Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche Scientifique et de
748 l'Innovation for permission to conduct research in the Moyen-Bafing National Park.
749 We thank the staff and researchers of the Moyen-Bafing Chimpanzee Project for
750 their invaluable assistance in data collection. Research was supported by
751 funding from the Wild Chimpanzee Foundation, the European Union's 8th
752 Framework Program, Horizon 2020 under grant agreement no. 802719, by two
753 Leakey Foundation grants, by the British Academy (Newton Fellowship
754 #NIFBA22\220640), and by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG; Emmy
755 Noether Fellowship 513871869).

756

757

758 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

759 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

760

761 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

762 The data that supports the findings of this study are available upon reasonable
763 request from the corresponding authors. All code for the analyses is available in our
764 Github repository: <https://github.com/Wild-Minds/AlgaeFishing>

765

766

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1161

1162 **TABLE AND FIGURE LEGENDS**

1163 **Table 1:** Summary of the terminology used to describe the behavioral repertoire of
1164 algae fishing by Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees, in increasing levels of granularity.
1165 Functional Behavioral Categories can include multiple Behaviors. Behaviors can be
1166 completed using multiple Behavioral Elements.

1167
1168 **Table 2:** Summary of terminology used to describe algae fishing by Moyen-Bafing
1169 chimpanzees at different levels of temporal specificity.

1170

1171 **Table 3:** Behaviors used by Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees when algae fishing to
1172 complete each Functional Behavioral Category. Whilst some Functional Behavioral
1173 Categories must be completed to successfully fish (Required), others can be added
1174 or omitted (Optional).

1175

1176 **Table 4:** Behavioral Elements used by Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees to algae fish.

1177

1178 **Table 5:** Comparison of repertoire sizes in different tool tasks used by chimpanzees,

1179 adapted from Estienne *et al.*, 2017.

1180

1181 ¹ Estienne *et al.*, 2017, ² Sanz & Morgan, 2010, ³ Sousa *et al.*, 2009, ⁴ Tonooka, 2001, ⁵ Boesch &

1182 Boesch, 1982, ⁶ Inoue-Nakamura & Matsuzawa, 1997, ⁷ Nishida & Hiraiwa, 1982.

1183 * *Transitions* refers to the number of steps in a sequence of tool-use behavior; these share overlap

1184 with—but are different to—our Functional Behavioral Categories, which can be skipped (minimum to

1185 complete the algae fishing sequence = 5), and each Functional Behavioral Category can contain

1186 multiple Behaviors, with transitions between them. Thus, the minimum number of transitions in algae

1187 fishing would be five.

1188 ** In Estienne *et al.*, Actions are similar to our category of Behavior, which in our case includes

1189 Actions, Grips, Retrieval Action, etc.

1190 *** Note that some of the studies reported in Estienne *et al.*, with a large number of Actions (by their

1191 definition), include items that we would classify as Behavioral Elements (of which algae fishing has

1192 $n=64$).

1193

1194

1195 **Figure 1:** The order of Functional Behavioral Categories completed as part of algae

1196 fishing Sessions at Moyen-Bafing. Straight arrows represent the temporal flow of

1197 Functional Behavioral Categories. Curved arrows represent repetitions, which could

1198 include adjustment of the fishing technique. Brackets indicate the Functional

1199 Behavioral Categories that comprise each Session, Sequence, and Dip.

1200

1201 **Figure 2:** Examples of the five Behavioral Elements for Grip used by Moyen-Bafing

1202 chimpanzees when holding their tools for algae fishing. See Table 4 for detailed

1203 definitions. Illustrations by © Stefano Lucchesi

1204

1205 **Figure 3:** Actions used by Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees while fishing for algae. Note

1206 that Swivel was divided into Swivel-inwards and Swivel-outwards (and Swivel-

1207 unclear). See Table 4 for detailed definitions. Image credit © Moyen Bafing

1208 Chimpanzee Project.

1209

1210 **Figure 4.** The number of elements of Grip and Action reaching an asymptote over

1211 the number of dips coded in our dataset. Our dataset comprises 1652 Dips with

1212 observable Actions and 1881 Dips with observable Grips. The asymptote was

1213 reached (i.e. reached full diversity) at 306 Dips for Grips, and 102 Dips for Actions.

1214

1215 **Figure 5.** Chimpanzee algae fishing hand preference. **A)** Handedness Index for

1216 individual chimpanzees' hand preferences while fishing. A handedness Index (HI) of

1217 -1 indicates exclusive left-hand use and 1 indicates exclusive right-hand use within a

1218 Session. We report HI scores for eight adults (two females, six males), each with ≥ 5

1219 Sessions, observed fishing across 15 pools (mean 3.5pools/individual; range = 2-6,

1220 ± 1.51 SD). Green circle area scales with the number of Sessions per individual

1221 (range = 5-27). For example, Adult Male 8 (AM_8) was observed in 27 Sessions; 26

1222 with a HI score of 1.0 (exclusive right-hand use), and 1 with an HI score of 0.95

1223 (near-exclusive right-hand use). **B)** Absolute Handedness Index (ABS HI) scores for

1224 fishing Actions. An ABS HI of 0 indicates even use of both hands across Dips for a

1225 given Action, and 1 indicates consistent use of the same hand for a given Action.

1226 Green circles show ABS HI scores for each Action and are scaled to the number of

1227 individuals with that score. Data include 36 adults (16 females, 20 males), each with
1228 ≥ 5 Dips per Action (Dunk n = 15 individuals; Swivel inward n = 8 individuals, Swivel
1229 outward n = 32 individuals, individuals can contribute to multiple Actions). For
1230 example, for Swivel Outwards, 32 individuals met this criterion: 19 had an ABS HI of
1231 1.0 (fully consistent hand use), and 13 had scores from 0.06 to 0.94, indicating near-
1232 even to near-consistent hand use, respectively.
1233
1234

Power

Tool held within palm, all fingers curled around it and thumb closed across fingers or opposing them, creating a fist-like configuration. Tool held in place by the force of squeezing the hand firmly.

Power-precision

Tool held against palm with fingers curled around it, but thumb (or finger) extends along shaft of tool. Grip maintained by squeezing fingers with the extended digit adding support.

Finger-hold

Tool held against the palmar surfaces of the fingers, with fingers curled around tool, but the thumb and palm does not participate in the grip. Tool is secured by squeezing the curled fingers around the tool.

Pinch

Tool held between the sides of adjacent fingers. Tool placement maintained by pressing sides of fingers together. The fingertips do not oppose each other nor contact the tool.

Precision

Tool held between two fingers. The fingertips oppose each other and apply force to hold tool, a third finger (usually index or middle) often runs along tool providing additional support.

Dunk
Tool enters water in a downwards motion

Sway
Tool moved up and down under the surface

Flick
Tool moved left to right under the surface

Swivel
Tool moved in circular motion, with hand rotating inwards or outwards from the body

Term	Definition
Functional Behavioral Category	<p>A broad, higher-order phase within a sequence of a complete behavior, encompassing essential sequential components of the overall task. Examples include 'acquiring a tool', performing the act of algae 'fishing', and 'retrieving algae' from the tool.</p> <p>Follows definitions with the same terminology of Byrne <i>et al.</i>, 2001; maps to the category level 'Activity' in Sanz & Morgan, 2009, and 'Sequence' in McGrew, 1974.</p>
Behavior	<p>A Behavior is a specific action employed by an individual to complete a given Functional Behavioral Category. For example, to fulfil the task of 'acquire tool', an individual may either collect an existing tool or manufacture a new tool.</p> <p>Follows definitions with the same terminology of Byrne <i>et al.</i>, 2001 and Sanz & Morgan, 2009.</p>
Behavioral Element	<p>A Behavioral Element describes the fine-scale method by which a Behavior is accomplished. For example, the Behavior 'tool creation' may involve specific Behavioral Elements such as 'clipping' or 'stripping' material from vegetation.</p> <p>Follows definitions with the same terminology by Byrne <i>et al.</i>, 2001, Sanz & Morgan, 2009, and Estienne <i>et al.</i>, 2017.</p>

Term	Definition
Session	A <i>Session</i> is marked from when a chimpanzee starts fishing to when they end the behavior. A session starts when a chimpanzee's hand or tool touches the water. A session ends when a chimpanzee: (a) stops fishing, tool making, or eating and leaves the field of view, or (b) engages in another non-tool related behavior for more than 30 seconds. A session can involve multiple sequences (<i>see Sequence</i>).
Sequence	A <i>Sequence</i> is marked from when a chimpanzee dips their tool or hand into the water and ends when they: (a) eat the algae, or (b) are unsuccessful and decide to terminate their fishing session. A sequence can involve multiple Dips (<i>see Dip</i>).
Dip	A <i>Dip</i> is marked from when a chimpanzee's tool enters the water and ends when: (a) the hand leaves the water, or (b) the chimpanzee loses contact with the tool. A Dip can be successful (the chimpanzee retrieves algae) or unsuccessful (the chimpanzee does not retrieve the tool or (sufficient) algae).

Behavior	Required for Functional Behavioral Category?	Description
Functional Behavioral Category: Acquire Tool		
<i>Collect tool</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee enters camera view with a tool or re-uses an existing tool.
<i>Create tool</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee constructs a tool, either by clipping or stripping the tool.
<i>Adjust tool</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee adjusts an existing tool, either by clipping or stripping the tool.
Functional Behavioral Category (Optional): Find Algae		
<i>Inspect water</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee visually inspects the water before or during the Session.
<i>Search edge</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee walks along the edge of the pool while looking towards the water. Must include movement of the chimpanzee along at least part of the edge of the pool while checking the water.
<i>Head bob inspection</i>	Optional	Outside of a Dip, the chimpanzee moves their head back and forth or up and down in a fluid repetitive motion whilst looking at the water.
Functional Behavioral Category: Prepare		
<i>Position self</i>	Required	Position in which the chimpanzee fishes, including if the chimpanzee uses items in their environment for support.
<i>Clear debris</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee clears debris from the surface of the water, either with a tool or with their hand.
Functional Behavioral Category: Fish		
<i>Grip choice</i>	Required	How the chimpanzee holds the tool.
<i>Grip where on tool</i>	Required	Where the chimpanzee holds the tool.
<i>Action</i>	Required	Movement of the tool in the water.
<i>Head bob</i>	Optional	Within a Dip, chimpanzee moves their head back and forth or up and down in a fluid repetitive motion whilst looking at the water.
<i>Sympathetic mouth movements</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee mouth and lip movements that accompany fine manual motor movements, and that do not appear to have a functional component (e.g., for breathing, eating, vocalizing; <i>sensu</i> : Waters & Fouts, 2002).

Functional Behavioral Category: Retrieval		
<i>Retrieval Action</i>	Required	Chimpanzee moves algae from end of tool towards mouth.
<i>Body parts involved in retrieval</i>	Required	Body parts used by chimpanzee to retrieve algae from tool.
<i>Algae transfer</i>	Optional	Algae is transferred from the fishing chimpanzee to another individual.
Functional Behavioral Category: Eat Algae		
<i>Eating Action</i>	Required	Chimpanzee removes algae from the tool into their mouth.
Functional Behavioral Category (Optional): Remove Debris		
<i>Remove debris</i>	Optional	Chimpanzee removes undesired material from the tool or their mouth.
Functional Behavioral Category: Finish with Tool		
<i>Discard tool</i>	Optional	Session ends when the chimpanzee abandons the tool.
<i>Tool transfer</i>	Optional	Session ends when the tool is transferred to another individual. Transfer is a Behavior in which a tool is passed directly from one chimpanzee (the primary user) to another, or when another chimpanzee acquires the tool within one second of the primary user discarding it. See Table 4 below for further detail on types of transfer.
<i>Carry tool</i>	Optional	Session ends when the chimpanzee carries tool away from the pool, out of camera view.

Functional Behavioral Category: Acquire Tool	
Behavior: Collect tool	
Arrive with a single tool	Chimpanzee enters camera view carrying a tool.
Arrive with multiple tools	Chimpanzee enters camera view carrying two or more tools.
Re-use others' tool	The chimpanzee uses a tool that another chimpanzee has previously used. To count as re-use, the coder must have seen another chimpanzee use that tool that day. Where it was unclear if a tool was the same as one used earlier that day, it was marked as a new tool. A chimpanzee can adjust this tool, and it would be marked as re-use of another individual's tool.
Behavior: Create tool	
Clip	Use of mouth or hands to remove material in a manner that creates a clean break where the detachment point is relatively smooth and even.
Strip	Use of mouth or hands to create tears using a pulling action, where the detachment point is longer and uneven.
Behavior: Adjust tool	
Clip	Use of mouth or hands to remove material in a manner that creates a clean break where the detachment point is relatively smooth and even.
Strip	Use of mouth or hands to create tears using a pulling action, where the detachment point is longer and uneven.
Functional Behavioral Category: Find Algae	
Behavior: Inspect water	
Inspection on arrival at pool	Before a Session begins, chimpanzee visually inspects the water.
Inspection during Session	During a Session, chimpanzee visually inspects the water.
Behavior: Search edge	
Search edge on arrival at pool	Before a Session, chimpanzee walks along the edge of the pool while visually inspecting the water.
Search edge during Session	During a Session, chimpanzee walks along the edge of the pool while visually inspecting the water.
Behavior: Head bop inspection	
Inspection head bop	Outside of a Dip, the chimpanzee moves their head back and forth or up and down in a fluid repetitive motion whilst looking at the water.
Functional Behavioral Category: Prepare	
Behavior: Position self	
Stand	The chimpanzee has exactly three limbs in contact with the ground (the other will be used when fishing). This includes crouch positions. Configuration while fishing or preparing to fish was always two feet and one hand in contact with ground.
Sit	The chimpanzee's ischial callosities are in contact with the ground, while their upper body is not.
Bipedal	Only the chimpanzee's feet are in contact with the ground.

Lay	Chimpanzee's upper body is in contact with the ground.
Hang branch	The chimpanzee is using one (or more) of their limbs to hang from a plant. Includes any instance where the chimpanzee is using a plant as an anchor. Only observed in combination one of the other Behavioral Elements for this Behavior.
Hang rock	The chimpanzee is using one (or more) of their extremities to hang from a rock. Includes any instance where the chimpanzee is using a rock as an anchor. Only observed in combination one of the other Behavioral Elements for this Behavior.
Behavior: Clear debris	
Clear debris	Chimpanzee uses a part of their body or the tool to displace debris from the surface of the water.
Functional Behavioral Category: Fish	
Behavior: Grip choice (see Figure 2)	
Pinch	The tool is held between the sides (not the pads) of two adjacent fingers (typically the index and middle fingers). The tool placement is maintained by pressing the sides of the fingers together. The fingertips do not oppose each other nor contact the tool directly.
Power	The tool is held within the palm, with all fingers curled around it and the thumb closed across the fingers or opposing them, creating a fist-like configuration. The tool is held in place by the force of squeezing the hand firmly in this fist position.
Precision	The tool is held between two fingers (usually the thumb and index, or thumb and middle fingers). The distal phalanges (fingertips) oppose each other and apply force to hold the tool, a third finger (usually the index or middle) often runs along the tool providing additional support.
Power-Precision	This grip combines features of the power and precision grips. The tool is held against the palm with the fingers curled around it (as in a power grip), but the thumb (or another finger) is extended along the shaft of the tool rather than folded into the fist. The grip is maintained by squeezing the fingers around the tool, with the extended digit adding support or control.
Finger hold	The tool is held against the palmar surfaces of the fingers, with the fingers curled around the tool, but the thumb and palm does not participate in the grip. The tool is secured by squeezing the curled fingers around the tool, pressing the tool against the bases of the fingers. The thumb does not contact the tool.
Behavior: Grip where on tool	
1/5 (end)	Tool is held at the part of the tool closest to the chimpanzee.
1/4	Hand is placed at approximately 1/4 (25%) of the total tool length from the end closest to the chimpanzee.
1/3	Hand is placed at approximately 1/3 (33%) of the total tool length from the end closest to the chimpanzee.
1/2	Hand is placed at approximately 1/2 (50%) of the total tool length.
2/3	Hand is placed at approximately 2/3 (66%) of the total tool length from the end closest to the chimpanzee.

3/4	Hand is placed at approximately 3/4 (75%) of the total tool length from the end closest to the chimpanzee. Note this was not observed.
4/5	Hand is placed at approximately 4/5 (80%) of the total tool length from the end closest to the chimpanzee. Note this was not observed.
Behavior: Action (see Figure 3)	
Swivel	<p>The distal end of the tool is submerged in water. The chimpanzee then moves the distal tip in a circular motion within the water (i.e. the hand and tool make the motion that would be used to trace a circle or spiral).</p> <p>This movement can be further divided to: <i>Swivel inwards</i>: The chimpanzee rotates the tool so that the distal end moves in a circular path towards the animal's body midline. (i.e. left hand + clockwise rotation or right hand + anti-clockwise rotation). <i>Swivel outwards</i>: The chimpanzee rotates the tool so that the distal end moves in a circular path away from the body's midline. (i.e. left hand + anti-clockwise rotation or right hand + clockwise rotation).</p>
Sway	The distal end of the tool is submerged in water. The chimpanzee moves the tip of the tool that is under the water in a horizontal, side-to-side motion (left to right and/or right to left), parallel to the water surface multiple times.
Dunk	The distal end of the tool is inserted vertically downward into the water (along the vertical axis, approximately at a 30-60° angle to the water's surface), with minimal to no horizontal or lateral movement after being submerged. After reaching a certain depth or briefly remaining submerged, the tool is withdrawn vertically (primarily perpendicular to the surface) from the water.
Flick	The distal end of the tool is inserted into the water and moved in a sharp up-and-down motion (i.e. along a vertical axis, perpendicular to the water's surface), so that the distal end moves sharply upward and downward one or more times while submerged. After performing this motion, the tool is withdrawn from the water.
Behavior: Head bop	
Head bop	The chimpanzee moves their head back and forth or up and down in a fluid repetitive motion whilst looking at the water.
Behavior: Sympathetic mouth movements	
Sympathetic mouth movements	Chimpanzee mouth movements that accompany fine manual motor movements, and that do not appear to have a functional component (e.g., for breathing, eating, vocalizing; <i>sensu</i> : Waters & Fouts, 2002).
Functional Behavioral Category: Retrieval	
Behavior: Retrieval Action	
Straight to self	The chimpanzee brings the end of the tool directly to a body part (typically the hand or mouth) without moving the fishing hand's

	position on the tool. This Action usually occurs using just the fishing hand, but other body parts can be used.
Shimmy tool	The chimpanzee brings the end of the tool to themselves by feeding the tool through their hand(s) or feet. The fishing hand moves away from the proximal end of the tool and closer to the side of the tool that contains the algae.
Behavior: Body parts involved retrieval	
Left hand retrieval	Left hand assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Right hand retrieval	Right hand assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Left arm retrieval	Left arm assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Right arm retrieval	Right arm assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Left foot retrieval	Left foot assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Right foot retrieval	Right foot assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Mouth retrieval	Mouth assists in bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Other body part retrieval	Any other body part was involved bringing the distal end of the tool with the algae back towards the chimpanzee.
Behavior: Algae transfer	
Algae transfer	At least part of the retrieved algae is transferred to another chimpanzee.
Functional Behavioral Category: Eat Algae	
Behavior: Eating Action	
Side swipe mouth	The chimpanzee closes their mouth around the tool and pulls the tool sideways through their mouth to collect the algae.
Side swipe hand	The chimpanzee closes their hand around the tool and pulls the tool sideways through their hand to collect the algae.
Mouth pick	The chimpanzee picks part of the algae off the tool using their mouth.
Hand pick	The chimpanzee picks part of the algae off the tool using their hand.
Hand assist	The chimpanzee uses their hand to assist in removing the algae, but the algae is not eaten from the assisting hand. For example, the chimpanzee may rest the algae hanging from the tool on their hand as they perform a side swipe mouth. This Action is always in addition to one of the other Behavioral Elements for this Behavior.
Other	None of the Behavioral Elements reported for this Behavior fit the eating Action used.
Hand	The chimpanzee does not use a tool and retrieves algae from the pool directly with their hand.
Functional Behavioral Category: Remove	
Behavior: Remove debris	

Retrieval remove debris	Debris is removed from the tool.
Functional Behavioral Category: Finish with Tool	
<i>Behavior: Discard tool</i>	
Release tool on ground	The chimpanzee releases the tool from its grasp so that it falls freely or is placed onto the ground or a rock surface, without handing to another individual, or continued manipulation of the tool after release.
Release tool in water	Similar to 'Release tool on ground', however, the chimpanzee releases the tool from its grasp so that it is located entirely in the water.
Release tool on pool edge	Similar to 'Release tool in water', however the chimpanzee releases the tool from its grasp so that it sits partially in the water and partially on the ground.
<i>Behavior: Tool transfer</i>	
Tool transfer: intolerant	<p>Transfer is a Behavior in which a tool is passed directly from one chimpanzee (the primary user) to another, or when another chimpanzee acquires the tool within one second of the primary user discarding it.</p> <p>Tool transfer is considered "intolerant" when a tool passes from one chimpanzee (the primary user) to another, either directly or within one second of the primary user discarding the tool, and the primary user appears reluctant to relinquish it. During an intolerant transfer, the recipient is actively attempting to take possession of the tool, such as by reaching for, grabbing, or pulling at it <u>and</u> the primary user exhibits negative behavior—such as facial expressions associated with negative arousal (e.g., bare-teeth display), gestures associated with negation (e.g., flings), vocalizations indicating negative arousal (e.g., screams, whimpers), or aggressive or submission behavior (e.g., crouching, hitting) during or immediately after the transfer. Intolerant transfers are distinguished from tolerant ones by the clear demonstration of resistance or negative affect on the part of the primary tool user.</p>
Tool transfer: tolerant	Transfer is when the tool is passed to another chimpanzee directly, or within one second, of the primary user discarding the tool. Here, the other chimpanzee is more active in taking the tool, and the primary user shows no negative behaviors once the tool has been transferred.
Tool transfer: Active	Transfer is when the tool is passed to another chimpanzee directly, or within one second, of the primary user discarding the tool. Here, the primary user is more active in giving the tool and also shows no negative behaviors once the tool has been transferred.
Tool transfer: unclear	Transfer is when the tool is passed to another chimpanzee directly, or within one second, of the primary user discarding the tool. Here, it is not clear if the transfer was intolerant, tolerant, or active.
Behavior: Carry tool	

Carry tool away	The chimpanzee takes the tool and moves with it so that both the tool and the individual carrying it leave the camera's field of view.
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<i>Tool-task</i>	<i>Higher order category*</i>	<i>Detailed category**</i>
Algae fishing (this study)	Functional Behavioral Category (7)	Behaviors (21) <i>Behavioral Elements (64)***</i>
Underground honey extraction ¹	Transitions (3)	Actions (14-17)
Arboreal honey extraction ^{1,2}	Transitions (3)	Actions (18)
Leaf Sponging ^{1,2}	Transitions (2)	Actions (7)
Leaf Sponging ^{1,3}	NA	Actions (6)
Leaf Sponging ^{1,4}	NA	Actions (7)
Nut Cracking ^{1,5}	Transitions (3)	Actions (4)
Nut Cracking ^{1,6}	NA	Actions (26)***
Termite Fishing (elevated nests) ^{1,7}	NA	Actions (3)
Termite Fishing (elevated nests) ^{1,2}	Transitions (2)	Actions (13)
Termite Fishing (subterranean nests) ^{1,2}	Transitions (3)	Actions (16)

1 SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

2 A full protocol for behavioral coding, including all variables and definitions is
3 available here: <https://github.com/Wild-Minds/AlgaeFishing>

4
5 *STRANGE: assessing potential sample biases.*

6 The STRANGE framework is a framework to report socio-ecological features which
7 may impact findings from the study sample (Webster & Rutz, 2020). STRANGE
8 works to highlight sampling bias by addressing seven categories which may be a
9 source of bias: Social background, Trapability and self-selection, Rearing history,
10 Acclimation and habituation, Natural changes in responsiveness, Genetic make-up,
11 and Experience. Below, we summarize each category for Moyen-Bafing
12 chimpanzees.

13
14 **Social Background:** At present, limited information is available regarding the social
15 background of Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees. The communities of Moyen-Bafing
16 chimpanzees are estimated to be ~37-58 individuals (Debetencourt *et al.* 2024),
17 relatively typical community sizes for the subspecies (Wilson *et al.*, 2014).
18 Preliminary results suggest an adult sex ratio of 1.32 (Debetencourt *et al.*, 2024),
19 which is higher than that described for forest populations (Badihi *et al.*, 2022) but is
20 similar to other savannah populations (Wilson *et al.*, 2014). A larger sex ratio may
21 result in greater male-male competition (Wilson *et al.*, 2014; Pruett *et al.*, 2017);
22 however, Western chimpanzees are suggested to be more gregarious and tolerant
23 than other chimpanzee subspecies (Boesch *et al.*, 2008; Wilson *et al.*, 2014). As a
24 result, Moyen-Bafing chimpanzees may not experience increased competition and

25 aggression as a result of sex-based demographics, as compared to other studied
26 chimpanzee communities.

27

28 **Trapability and self-selection:** This study uses video data collected using camera
29 traps. Chimpanzees who have had very little exposure to humans and/or human
30 artefacts may react with caution to new objects in their environment. At other
31 chimpanzee field sites, individuals have shown variation in their response to camera
32 traps, which may result in some individuals being less likely to be recorded
33 (Caravaggi *et al.*, 2020). Chimpanzees at the MBCP have been exposed to camera
34 traps since 2013 as part of the Pan-African Program (Debetencourt *et al.*, 2024).
35 They show interest in the cameras and continue to acknowledge their presence
36 when passing by. We recognize that camera trap data may lead to some level of
37 self-selection, but likely less so than direct observation (Hobaiter *et al.*, 2017) and we
38 have recorded a large number of individuals on the camera traps, including all age
39 and both sex classes.

40 Alongside self-selection, our choice in position of the camera traps may
41 impact the individuals included in our study. When choosing camera location,
42 researchers have large areas in which to search for evidence of algae fishing. When
43 and where algae will grow remains difficult to predict, making it possible that some
44 pools were not camera trapped when chimpanzees were fishing.

45

46 **Rearing History:** All chimpanzees are wild born, with no direct influence from
47 humans.

48

49 **Acclimation and habituation:** None of the individuals included in this study were
50 habituated to direct observation.

51

52 **Natural changes in responsiveness:** As wild animals, individuals had complete
53 freedom when deciding when and how to fish for algae. While behavioral changes
54 may occur when algae fishing over time, these do not negatively impact our
55 exploration of variation when algae fishing. Individuals fishing in pools located at
56 boundary areas between community territories may express higher levels of arousal
57 because of the risk of agonistic (or even lethally aggressive) behavior from
58 neighboring groups (Wilson *et al.*, 2003; Mitani & Watts, 2005). As territories for the
59 communities have not yet been fully described, it remains unclear which specific
60 pools were located in boundary areas and/or were accessed by multiple
61 communities. Increased arousal may lead to variation in algae fishing expression;
62 however, we focused our description of the repertoire and program of actions across
63 individuals at the population level.

64

65 **Genetic Makeup:** Female chimpanzees emigrate to a new community during
66 adolescence, and there are no site-specific barriers to transfer of females between
67 communities at MBCP, making the influence of systematic genetic differences on
68 algae fishing behavior less likely.

69

70 **Experience:** Chimpanzees at Moyen-Bafing have had camera traps present in their
71 territories since 2013 (Debetencourt *et al.*, 2024) and therefore have long-term
72 experience with camera traps. This exposure reduces the impact of self-selection or
73 unusual behavior. As experience in algae fishing may vary across areas and

74 individuals, we limited our data to adult individuals, and included 62 individuals

75 fishing from pools across a diverse set of locations in the study area.

76

77 **Table S1: Dataset of adult chimpanzee algae fishing by pool.** The number of
78 adult individuals in the dataset observed fishing in each pool, along with how many
79 Dips were coded for that pool. Total number of adult individuals in the dataset is 62,
80 but the same individual can fish in more than one area.

Pool	No. Males	No. Females	No. Dips
1	5	2	487
2	1	3	9
3	2	1	10
4	3	0	7
5	3	4	497
6	1	0	12
7	3	1	233
8	5	3	228
9	5	2	254
10	5	3	85
11	4	1	171
12	3	4	50
13	1	0	6
14	2	0	16
15	1	3	19
16	2	1	15
17	6	2	70
18	4	1	57
19	2	2	14
20	4	1	17
21	2	4	158

81

82

83 **Table S2.** Interobserver reliability values across 12 variables. We included 144 Dips
84 within 38 Sessions, where n= number of times that Variable was coded for
85 Interobserver reliability.

Variable	n	Cohen's Kappa (SE)	95% confidence	Percentage agreement
Arrive tool ¹	35	0.930 (0.046)	0.862 – 1.000	97.1
Tool create ²	37	0.881 (0.065)	0.754 – 1.000	91.9
Body part fish	144	0.927 (0.032)	0.864 – 1.000	96.5
Grip	144	0.847 (0.034)	0.781 – 0.914	88.2
Body position	144	0.975 (0.018)	0.940 – 1.000	98.2
Action	144	0.923 (0.028)	0.868 – 0.978	95.1
Head bob	144	0.813 (0.055)	0.706 – 0.920	92.4

Body part retrieve	144	0.961 (0.019)	0.923 – 0.999	97.1
Retrieval	144	0.937 (0.028)	0.882 – 0.991	96.5
Eating technique	144	0.912 (0.035)	0.844 – 0.980	95.1
Tool use end	38	0.928 (0.049)	0.882 – 1.000	94.7
Clear debris	144	0.971 (0.029)	0.915 – 1.000	99.3

86 ¹ Weighted Kappa as ordinal categories

87

88

89

90 **Figure S1:** Schema of algae fishing program with three levels: Functional Behavioral

91 Categories, Behaviors, and Behavioral Elements

92